

1 **An ETI factor expressed in human HSC.**

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6 FLYWCH1 is a human orthologue of effector triggered immunity NBD-LRR WRKY transcription factors in
7 plants that function in disease resistance (R) in plants. We recently discovered FLYWCH1 homology with
8 the WRKY transcription factors from *Arabidopsis* and demonstrated its regulation by pattern recognition of
9 the bacterial pathogen-associated molecular pattern muramyl dipeptide (MDP) and the pattern recognition
10 receptor NOD2. Here we describe FLYWCH1 expression in hematopoietic stem cells in humans. In HSC,
11 FLYWCH1 resides under the control of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AHR), and in aged but not young
12 HSC, FLYWCH1 is expressed in an AHR-dependent manner. FLYWCH1 is expressed in multiple cell
13 types of the immune system but repressed in the Th17 lineage despite its control by AhR. FLYWCH1
14 expression is regulated in a lineage-selective manner in the human hematopoietic system.
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Results

I. FLYWCH1 is expressed in human HSC.

GSE191338

n=3 human CD34+ cord blood stem progenitor cells (EPCR negative)

n=3 human CD34+ cord blood stem progenitor cells (EPCR positive)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84256	1.12e-05	0.208	-4.39	-0.9138307	238.02	FLYWCH1	1605/17570	90.9

FLYWCH1 expression was enriched in an EPCR+ CD34+ HSPC fraction concentrated in HSC, based on expression of genes with high expression in human HSC, including HLF, AVP, PRDM16, and FGD5 (Figure 1).

II. FLYWCH1 expression dynamics in the Th₁₇ lineage.

GSE102045

n=6 human PBMC

n=6 Th17 cells from human PBMC

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84256	3.25e-03	0.132	2.9428775	0.38840473	945.03	FLYWCH1	918/15676	94.1

FLYWCH1 expression, interestingly, was down-regulated in Th17 cells (Figure 2).

III. Deletion of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor results in loss of FLYWCH1 expression.

GSE67378

n=5 wild-type HSC (18 months)

n=5 AHR KO HSC (18 months) (Ahr -/-)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
17341608	6.51e-02	2.08	-4.3	5.77e-01	FLYWCH1	2003/41345	95.2

Deletion of the AhR resulted in loss of FLYWCH1 expression, demonstrating strong interaction between the gut tolerance AhR system and the ETI factor FLYWCH1.

IV. AhR control of FLYWCH1 is less prominent in young HSC.

GSE46976

n=3 HSC (wild-type, C57bl/6); 8 weeks of age

n=4 HSC AhR KO (Ahr -/-); 8 weeks of age

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
17341608	3.56e-01	0.9855975	-4.6	0.3917445	FLYWCH1	13733/36310	62.2

1 V. FLYWCH1 is expressed in the Mk/E lineage where it is expressed under the control of AhR signaling.

2 GSE167866

3 *n*=3 CD34+ CD41+, 7 days differentiation from CD34+ cells (human peripheral blood)

4 *n*=3 CD34+ CD41+, 7 days differentiation in the presence of AhR antagonist S1 from CD34+ cells (human
5 peripheral blood)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84256	1.78e-02	0.2797	-2.370585	-0.66312	298.62	FLYWCH1	451/16101	97.2

7 In human megakaryocytes, FLYWCH1 existed under the control of AhR: CD34+ CD41+,
8 differentiation in the presence of AhR antagonist resulted in significant activation of FLYWCH1.

9 Discussion

10 We described here expression of an ETI (effector-triggered immunity) factor with homology to *R*
11 (resistance) innate immune receptors from the plant kingdom, FLYWCH1, in human hematopoietic stem
12 cells. FLYWCH1 expression was regulated in a lineage-selective manner in the human hematopoietic
13 system, with developmental-stage specific expression dynamics in murine HSC. FLYWCH1 lies under the
14 control of the aryl hydrocarbon signaling system that modulates tolerance in the gut.
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